

RESONANT VIBRATION NONLINEARITY IN ACOUSTIC WAVE-DEFECT INTERACTION

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In this paper, the effect of vibration resonance on nonlinear ultrasonic response of defects is studied. Unlike the resonance of the whole specimen, the Local Defect Resonance (LDR) naturally provides an efficient energy pumping from the wave directly to the defect. The LDR-“amplifier”, therefore, exhibits transition to nonlinear regime at moderately low driving amplitude. In addition, the concept of the defect as a nonlinear oscillator brings about different dynamic and frequency scenarios in its nonlinear behaviour characteristic of the parametric oscillations. The experiments confirm unconventional nonlinear dynamics of simulated and realistic defects subject to LDR. The resonant nonlinear defects demonstrate threshold dynamics of instable vibrations, hysteresis, super- and subharmonic resonances with anomalously efficient generation of the higher harmonics and subharmonics.

1. Introduction

The nonlinear approach to ultrasonic non-destructive testing (NDT) is concerned with nonlinear material response, which is inherently related to the frequency changes of the input signal (e.g. higher harmonics (HH)). For propagating ultrasonic waves, the effects of nonlinearity manifest at moderately high input power (intensity $\sim 1 \text{ W/cm}^2$) when a local material stiffness becomes dependent on the wave amplitude (material nonlinearity). However, this type of nonlinearity turned out to be rather inefficient: for all homogeneous and free from defects materials, the stiffness variation is usually below 10^{-3} even for high ultrasonic strains $\approx 10^{-4}$.

A substantial increase in nonlinearity was found in materials with imperfections and cracked defects: an important role in this enhancement is played by internal boundaries of the defects, which provide constraints to contact vibrations. A local stiffness changes due to intermittent contact between the fragments of the defect and thus causes nonlinearity of local “bimodular” vibrations (Contact Acoustic Nonlinearity (CAN)) [1]. The CAN mechanisms are concerned with “clapping” of crack planes (for vibrations normal to the interface) and nonlinear friction between the crack surfaces for tangential vibrations. Due to CAN, the spectrum of vibrations acquires multiple HH which are nonlinear NDE signatures of the cracked defects readily observable in experiments.

Besides the much higher efficiency, CAN was shown to exhibit a substantial qualitative departure from fundamental nonlinear effects of the higher harmonic generation. The family of “NDT tags” observed for nonlinear defects included frequency down-conversion (subharmonics), hysteresis, instabilities, chaotic dynamics, etc. [2]. To interpret such “unconventional” effects the damaged

area can be identified as a nonlinear oscillator (or a set of coupled nonlinear oscillators) and therefore exhibit both nonlinear and resonance properties. A direct experimental proof for the “resonant” defects has been obtained recently [3] and the concept of Local Defect Resonance (LDR) introduced.

In this paper, the effect of LDR on nonlinear ultrasonic response of defects is studied. Unlike the resonance of the whole specimen, the LDR naturally provides an efficient energy pumping from the wave directly to the defect thus increasing its nonlinear response. In addition, the concept of the defect as a nonlinear oscillator brings about qualitatively different dynamic and frequency scenarios characteristic of parametric oscillations. It is experimentally shown that the frequency- and spatially-selective ultrasonic activation of defects by using the concept of LDR is the way to optimize efficiency of nonlinear ultrasonic NDT.

2. Linear and nonlinear Local Defect Resonances

2.1 Concept and Experimental Evidence for LDR

The concept of a resonant defect is based on the fact that a cracked defect in the material diminishes its stiffness locally so that a certain mass of the material around the defect could manifest a local natural frequency of vibrations. A frequency match between the defect eigenfrequency and the probing ultrasonic wave causes a resonant increase of the vibration amplitude of the defect (LDR). A local stiffness and an effective mass of the defect are found by considering the potential and kinetic energies of the defect vibrations and are combined in a simple spring-mass LDR model [4].

A direct way to experimentally reveal LDR is to measure an individual contribution of each point of the specimen in its overall frequency response. For this purpose, an ultrasonic excitation by a wide-band piezoelectric transducer is combined with a laser vibrometer scan of the specimen surface. It enables to probe and indicate all possible resonances in every point of the specimen. The origin of each maximum is then verified by imaging the vibration pattern in the specimen at the corresponding frequency. Fig. 1 shows an example of the LDR vibration patterns measured for a square inset ($25 \times 25 \text{ mm}^2$) in a carbon fibre-reinforced polymer (CFRP). A strong enhancement (about 20 dB) of the vibration amplitude observed locally in the defect area is identified as a fundamental defect resonance (Fig. 1, a). Besides the fundamental LDR, zoom-in scan of the vibration field inside the defect area in a wider frequency range reveals the higher-order LDR with multiple nodal lines in the vibration patterns (Fig. 1, b, c). Such a methodology was successfully applied to a search of the LDR in a variety of materials. The example presented in Fig. 2 illustrates a clear evidence of LDR in kHz-frequency range for damage in honeycomb composite component.

Figure 1. Fundamental (a) and higher-order LDR (b, c) for a square inset in a CFRP plate.

Figure 2. Fundamental LDR in a honeycomb glass fibre-reinforced (GFRP) structure.

The ‘amplification’ of local defect vibrations depends on the LDR quality factor Q . A pair of LDR frequency responses measured for different defects in CFRP specimens (Fig. 3) demonstrates classical resonance frequency behaviour and shows that LDR can manifest a high Q resonance.

Figure 3. LDR frequency responses measured for impact induced fibre loss (left) and impact damage in 280x40x1 mm³ CFRP plate.

Similar to a conventional resonance, the value of Q factor determines the ‘amplification’ of local vibrations due to LDR. In fact, the solution to the equation of the forced defect vibrations in the presence of damping:

$$(1) \quad \ddot{x} + 2\lambda\dot{x} + \omega_0^2 x = F_0 \cos \nu t$$

is sought as a sum of the free and forced terms which for zero initial conditions and $\nu \approx \omega_0$ takes the form of the transient vibration:

$$(2) \quad x = x_0(1 - \exp(-\lambda t)) \cos \nu t ,$$

with the steady state amplitude $x_0 \approx F_0 / 2\lambda\omega_0 = (F_0 / \omega_0^2)Q$. This amplitude is $Q = \omega_0 / 2\lambda$ times higher than the vibration amplitude outside the resonance. By introducing Q value in (2) the exponential term takes the form $\exp(-(\pi / QT))$ which shows that Q periods of the driving signal T are required to reach the steady state ‘amplification’ of vibrations.

To verify the LDR ‘amplification’ process, the impact damaged specimen of CFRP (LDR shown in Fig. 3, right) was excited with a burst of ultrasound and the transient development of vibration was monitored with the laser vibrometer. The results in Fig. 4 show a good correspondence between the experiment and the calculations based on the above relations. The values of Q factors measured for other types of realistic defects in various materials ranged from ~ 10 to 100 so that the LDR induced amplification of local vibrations as high as ~ 20 -40 dB was observed.

2.2 LDR nonlinearity

Since LDR is as an efficient resonant ‘‘amplifier’’ of the local vibrations, one would expect it to contribute appreciably to defect nonlinearity. An extremely high resonant nonlinearity is demonstrated in Fig. 5 for a delamination in GFRP plate: Multiple HH generation is observed even at a moderate input voltage. A crucial role of the driving frequency match to LDR for nonlinearity increase is illustrated in Fig. 6 for a crack in a unidirectional (UD-) CFRP rod. As the driving frequency matches the LDR frequency (19.5 kHz), a strong enhancement of the HH amplitudes generated locally in the defect area is observed.

Figure 4. LDR time response of an impact damage in CFRP to an 85 period burst signal at LDR frequency 5180 Hz.

Figure 5. HH spectrum for delamination in GFRP specimen driven at LDR frequency 20900 Hz. Input voltage is 7 V.

Figure 6. HH LDR frequency response of a crack in CFRP rod (LDR frequency 19.5 kHz).

The results presented in Figs. 5 & 6 prove that at moderate input signals the LDR enhances appreciably the nonlinearity of defects via local “amplification” of vibrations. It raises substantially the efficiency of “conventional” nonlinear effects, like HH generation and wave mixing. However, this is not the only dynamic scenario of nonlinear phenomena for resonant defects. At higher level of excitation, a combined effect of LDR and nonlinearity can result in qualitatively new features characteristic of the nonlinear and parametric resonances.

2.2.1 Superharmonic resonances

For the superharmonic resonance, the input frequency is taken as $\approx \omega_0 / n$ and converted into ω_0 drive via the n th-order nonlinearity of the oscillator. The example given below corresponds to $n = 2$ and uses the perturbation approach for finding solutions to equation (1) with the second and third-order nonlinear terms added [5]:

$$(3) \quad \ddot{x} + 2\lambda\dot{x} + \omega_0^2 x + \alpha x^2 + \beta x^3 = F_0 \cos \nu t$$

For the driving frequency $\nu = (\omega_0 / 2) + \varepsilon$ and small λ , the solution of the first approximation is a linear driven vibration:

$$(4) \quad x_1 = \frac{4F_0}{3\omega_0^2} \cos[(\omega_0 / 2) + \varepsilon]t \quad .$$

The resonance driving force will be developed directly via quadratic nonlinearity so that after inserting (4) in (3) and keeping only resonant terms in the right hand side, one obtains:

$$(5) \quad \ddot{x}_2 + 2\lambda\dot{x}_2 + \omega_0^2 x_2 + \alpha x_2^2 + \beta x_2^3 = -\alpha x_1^2 \cos(\omega_0 + 2\varepsilon) \quad .$$

A solution to (5) could be readily found if one neglects the nonlinear terms of the second-order solution in the left-hand side:

$$(6) \quad x_2^{2\omega} = -\frac{4\alpha F_0^2}{9\omega_0^5 \sqrt{4\varepsilon^2 + \lambda^2}} \cos[(\omega_0 + 2\varepsilon)t] \quad .$$

A similar procedure for the input $\nu = (\omega_0 / 3) + \varepsilon$ leads to the solution for the resonant third HH:

$$(7) \quad x_2^{3\omega} = -\frac{\beta(x_1^0)^3}{8\omega_0 \sqrt{9\varepsilon^2 + \lambda^2}} \cos[(\omega_0 + 3\varepsilon)t],$$

where $x_1^0 = 9F_0 / 8\omega_0^2$.

Equations (6) & (7) confirm the resonant generation of the second and third higher harmonics. The maximal amplitudes of the superharmonic resonances reduce with n ($\sim F_0^n$) but also depend on the values of the high-order nonlinearity. Since a step-wise stiffness modulation by means of CAN enhances its higher-order parameters [1], one can expect a strong development of the HH resonances in resonant defects.

A direct proof of superharmonic resonances in defects is demonstrated for the third-order resonance in impact damaged CFRP specimen with LDR around 5140 Hz in Figs. 7 & 8. One-third of the LDR frequency (1714 Hz) was therefore selected for the excitation while the input voltage was increased up to 80 V. The spectrum (Fig. 7) and the vibration pattern (Fig. 8) measured in the defect area illustrate the dominance of the third harmonic vibration (period ~ 0.19 ms in Fig. 8).

Figure 7. Spectrum of the third-order superharmonic LDR in impact damaged CFRP plate.

Figure 8. Vibration pattern of the third-order superharmonic LDR in impact damaged CFRP plate.

2.2.2 Subharmonic and parametric resonances

Manifestation of parametric effects is due to the amplitude-dependent shift (modulation) of LDR frequency induced by the driving signal. The frequency shift induced by the driving signal causes a periodic modulation of the oscillator natural frequency that activates manifestation of the parametric resonance. The parametric approach (well developed and applied in many fields of physics) enables further to reveal other features of the nonlinear resonance phenomena.

The nonlinear source of parametric resonance effects can be disclosed by applying the perturbation method to equation (3). For the driving frequency close to the resonance $\nu = \omega_0 + \varepsilon$, the solution of the first approximation is a linear vibration:

$$(8) \quad x_1 = \frac{F_0}{2\omega_0 \sqrt{\varepsilon^2 + \lambda^2}} \cos \nu t \quad .$$

In the next approximation, the quadratic nonlinearity in (3) apparently produces the third-order interaction term $\sim 2\alpha x_1 x_2$. By using (8) and taking into account this term only, one obtains:

$$(9) \quad \ddot{x}_2 + 2\lambda\dot{x}_2 + \omega_0^2 \left[1 + \frac{\alpha F_0}{\omega_0^3 \sqrt{\varepsilon^2 + \lambda^2}} \cos \nu t \right] x_2 = 0$$

Equation (9) is a Mathieu's-type equation whose general form is [6]:

$$(10) \quad \ddot{x} + \omega_0^2 (1 + h \cos \gamma t) x = 0$$

and which is known to reveal parametric resonance and instability phenomena [6, 7].

The form (9) corresponds to the second-order parametric resonance at $\nu \approx \omega_0$. In this case, the frequencies of the solutions to (10) include the HH of the input signal: $\omega = n\nu$ ($n=1, 2, 3, \dots$) [7]. Beyond the input threshold, their amplitudes grow in time exponentially (instability).

In a similar way, for $\nu \approx 2\omega_0$ drive, the second approximation in (3) yields [5]:

$$(11) \quad \ddot{x}_2 + 2\lambda\dot{x}_2 + \omega_0^2 \left[1 - \frac{2\alpha F_0}{3\omega_0^4} \cos[(2\omega_0 + \varepsilon)t] \right] x_2 = 0$$

which is a condition for a subharmonic (fundamental parametric) resonance. In this case, the solutions to (11) comprise unstable ultra-subharmonic outputs: $\omega = m\nu/2$ ($m=1, 2, 3, \dots$) [7].

Unlike conventional (linear) resonance, in a certain range of detuning ε the parametric resonances provide an exponential growth of the vibration amplitudes in time even in the presence of damping. The instability develops as soon as the frequency modulation index h (input energy) exceeds a certain threshold determined by the energy dissipated in the system. The critical values of h are the functions of ε (and vice versa): the higher modulation is generally required for larger frequency mismatch thus producing divergent boundaries of the V-shaped $h(\varepsilon)$ curves for parametric resonances [7]. Thus, for high modulation amplitudes, the parametric resonances can be observed in broad frequency bands.

The experimental proof for unstable parametric dynamics of the HH (the second-order parametric resonance) is given in Fig. 9 for impact damage (LDR at 5140 Hz, Fig. 3, right) in CFRP sample. The nonlinear regime starts above a step-like instability threshold at ~ 30 V input (Fig. 9, a) and results in a strong nonlinear distortion of vibrations with highly nonlinear spectrum of HH (Fig. 9, b)). This behavior is in accord with general theoretical analysis for parametric resonances: beyond the threshold input at fundamental LDR frequency the parametric resonances are activated and provide an instable growth of the HH. The fundamental vibration is depleted due to the energy outflow and heavily distorted via frequency conversion to HH.

The parametric instability, therefore, turns LDR into strongly nonlinear resonance which is known to feature the fold-over resonance curves with the thresholds for the rise and fall of the nonlinear vibrations to exhibit bistability. This feature of the resonant defect nonlinearity is confirmed in Fig. 10 for the impact damage in CFRP driven at LDR frequency 5140 Hz with successive up- and down-input voltage variations.

Figure 9. Bifurcation nonlinear dynamics for LDR in CFRP plate: threshold for HH generation (a) and vibration distortion beyond the threshold (b).

Figure 10. Bistability of nonlinear resonances in CFRP sample.

The excitation frequency was then changed to the second harmonic (10280 Hz) of the fundamental LDR to observe a subharmonic resonance. The threshold for the resonance was found to be ≈ 45 V as illustrated in Figs. 11, a), b). Beyond the threshold, the subharmonic component increases dramatically and prevails in the vibration (velocity) spectrum: $V_{\omega/2} / V_{\omega} \approx 30$ dB at 10280 Hz input (Fig. 11, b)). This complies with pure sinusoidal subharmonic vibration pattern in the impact area beyond the threshold (Fig. 11, a)). The input frequency range for both subharmonic and superharmonic resonances was measured to be within ~ 100 -200 Hz that corresponds to a high Q factor of the LDR for this defect shown in Fig. 3 (right).

Figure 11. Subharmonic LDR for impact damage in CFRP: vibration patterns (a) and spectrum (b) beyond threshold input voltage 45 V.

3. Conclusions

In this paper, it is proposed to use a combination of nonlinearity with Local Defect Resonance (LDR) to enhance substantially the nonlinear frequency conversion by the defects. Since LDR is as an efficient resonant “amplifier” of the local vibrations, it manifests a profound nonlinearity even at moderate ultrasonic excitation level. The “classical” nonlinear effects, like HH are not the only dynamic scenario of nonlinear phenomena for resonant defects. A combined effect of LDR and nonlinearity results in qualitatively new “nonclassical” features characteristic of nonlinear and parametric resonances.

The experiments confirm unconventional nonlinear dynamics of realistic defects subject to LDR and demonstrate that the nonlinear resonance and parametric dynamics should be seen not as exceptional or anomalous but rather conventional and peculiar to majority of defects in the resonance conditions. The threshold transition to a strongly nonlinear resonance mode is accompanied by instability of vibrations. Beyond the threshold, the instability ceases and the vibration returns to stability via a strong rise of nonlinear frequency up-conversion. Such a bifurcation type development of instability and transition between linear and nonlinear vibration modes contributes to dynamic hysteresis for the fundamental and the higher harmonic vibrations of the defect.

According to the experiments, under resonance conditions the HH and subharmonic components may dominate in the vibration spectrum of defects. This suggests nonlinear LDR application as an extremely efficient mode in nonlinear NDT. Besides, both super- and subharmonic LDR are strongly localised in the defect area that provides a background for high-contrast defect-selective imaging.

Acknowledgement

The author acknowledges support of this study in the framework of ALAMSA project funded from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under grant agreement no. 314768.

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